

Diamagnetism of Bismuth and Antimony in the Colloidal State.

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Soon after the publication of Vaidyanathan's work, (*Indian J. Phys.*, 1930, 5, 559), which showed that the diamagnetic susceptibility of bismuth, antimony and graphite decreases on powdering, Bhatnagar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 957) pointed out that the absence of impurities in the form of oxide or sub-oxides of the elements in question, particularly bismuth and antimony, and the absorbed gases must be made sure of, before accepting any effect of mechanical colloidisation on diamagnetic susceptibilities. Mathur and Verma (*Indian J. Phys.*, 1931, 6, 181) developed this view and showed that the original value of bismuth can be regained if the oxides are suitably removed. The same point was emphasised about antimony later (*Proc. Ind. Sci. Congress., Chem. Sec.*, 1932). Rao (*Indian J. Phys.*, 1931, 6, 241) claimed that below a definite size corresponding with the size of the macrocrystal* a rapid change in the susceptibility of bismuth ensues. Vaidyanathan and others too have stressed the same point on the susceptibility measurements of chemically prepared gold (Vaidyanathan and Singh, *Nature*, 1931, 128, 302) and silver sols (Vaidyanathan and Puri, *ibid.*, 1932, 129, 170). It seems, however, that in trying to get rid of the oxide impurity, Rao has forgotten that impurities in the form of carbonates, bicarbonates, etc., can also be obtained if the powdering is done under water (Mellor, "Treatises on Inorganic Chemistry", Vol. IX, p. 626), as has actually been done by him. With a view to avoid contamination due to these impurities, bismuth has been reinvestigated, the powdering being done under liquid paraffin, for particle sizes much smaller than those reported in our communication already referred to. Antimony has also been investigated along the same lines as bismuth, as it also exhibits magnetic anisotropy. Another point of interest which made us undertake this work is that

* Quoted by Rao.

antimony is capable of being oxidised very easily. It is very probable, therefore, that oxidation has a good deal to do with the observed decrease in the susceptibility obtained by Vaidyanathan and Rao (*loc. cit.*), for the lowest size ($150\mu\mu$) reached by the former is not so low as to be able to affect the lattice electrons encircling a larger number of atoms as put forward by Ehrenfest (*Physica*, 1925, 3, 388). The changes observed on powdering in the case of bismuth and antimony are capable of a satisfactory explanation on chemical grounds only as shown by the results of the investigation described below.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Bismuth was powdered in the first stages under liquid paraffin and later under benzene to check oxidation as much as possible. Particles were graded out into different sizes by shaking the paraffin-free powders with benzene and removing the layers settling down at different intervals of time. The sizes were determined by means of a Leitz high magnification power microscope and the magnetic susceptibilities by means of a torsional balance of the Curie-Wilson type. The powders were also investigated after removing the oxide impurity by means of tartaric acid and the values so obtained are placed in the last column of the following table for the sake of comparison.

TABLE I.

Substance.	Magnetic susceptibility $\times 10^{-6}$	
	Before removing the oxide.	After removing the oxide.
Bismuth	-1.27	
Coarse powder ($1\mu-1.2\mu$)	-0.84	-1.27
Fine powder (0.7μ)	-0.72	-1.233

Investigation on antimony was divided into the following parts:

1. Powdering the metal in air for different intervals of time and investigating the samples so obtained along with the coagula obtained by sparking between the metal electrodes under conductivity water.

2. Detecting and estimating the oxide purity.
3. Removing the oxide impurity and investigating the samples magnetically.
4. Powdering the metal under inert liquids to check oxidation and to reinvestigate the samples.

The results obtained under different heads are described below in the above order.

1. *Powdering the metal at different intervals.*—Antimony was powdered in a well-polished agate mortar and powdered samples were collected at different intervals of time. The coagulum was obtained by sparking between the metal electrodes and coagulating by exhaustive cataphoresis.

TABLE II.

Current=1 Amp. Initial reading on the torsion head=128°·0'.

Substance.	Wt.	Final reading.	Torsion given.	Magnetic susceptibility $\times 10^{-6}$.	Particle size.
Water	0·1000 g.	238° 19'	110°·19'	-0·72	...
Capsule	1·7480	208°·48'	80°·48'
Antimony metal	0·1000	241°·3'	113°·3'	-0·812	...
Powder No. 1.	0·1000	231°·24'	103°24'	-0·568	5·0 μ
„ No. 2.	0·1000	229°·20'	101°·20'	-0·516	2·5
„ No. 3	0·1000	228°·42'	100°·42'	-0·499	1·5
„ No. 4	0·1000	228°·39'	100°·39'	-0·498	1·0
Coagula	...	„	...	-0·579	...

It is clear from the above table that the diamagnetism of antimony goes on decreasing with the particle size. The rate of decrease, however, becomes negligibly small when the particle size reaches 1·5 μ . Further powdering, therefore, appeared unnecessary. The smallest value for the diamagnetism of antimony obtained by Vaidyanathan is $-0\cdot536 \times 10^{-6}$. The value for the last powder in the above table is a little less, but our value for the coagulum is considerably higher than that obtained by Vaidyanathan (*loc. cit.*).

2. *Detection and estimation of the oxides.*—The presence of the oxides of antimony in the powders was determined as follows and is based upon the well known fact that whereas antimony metal does not dissolve in dilute hydrochloric acid, all its oxides are soluble therein. A small amount of the powder was, therefore, boiled with dilute hydrochloric acid, filtered and the filtrate was tested for antimony by the usual test with hydrogen sulphide. In every case a thick orange precipitate of antimony sulphide was obtained, proving beyond doubt, that the samples contain the oxides of the metal as impurity. In order to estimate the amount of this impurity in the sample, an attempt was made to remove the oxide completely by boiling with hydrochloric acid. It was then discovered that the oxide is rather tenacious and leaves the metal with great difficulty and so even on successive boilings with dilute hydrochloric acid could not be removed completely. A direct estimation of the antimony content of the samples, by the method given below was, therefore, resorted to (Scott, "Standard Methods of Chemical Analysis", Vol. I). It is known that nitric acid oxidises antimony from trivalent to pentavalent type, which then reacts with potassium iodide to liberate iodine according to the reaction :

and this amount of iodine liberated can be estimated by titrating against sodium thiosulphate :

Equal quantities of the powders (0.1 g.) were in each case, therefore, dissolved in a mixture of hydrochloric acid (10 c.c.) and concentrated nitric acid (1 c.c.). Excess of nitric acid was boiled off and the sides of the flask thoroughly rinsed with 1:1 dilute hydrochloric acid. The whole volume was made up to 60 c.c. by adding distilled water and 3 c. c. of 20 % potassium iodide solution. This was then titrated against standard thiosulphate solution, the end point being noted by the disappearance of the red colour from CS_2 already added to the solution. For the success of experiment it was, however, necessary to keep the solution very cold during all this interval.

The concentrations of the various samples tried in terms of antimony are given below. The samples are the same as those tried in Table II.

TABLE III.

Sodium thiosulphate soln. conc. = 0.09024N.

Substance	Wt.	Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ soln.	Sb content.	Sb in the samples.
Antimony	0.1000 g.	18.45 c.c.	0.1000 g.	100.0%
Powder No. 1	0.1000	17.5	0.0948	94.8
„ No. 2	0.1000	17.0	0.092	92.0
„ No. 3	0.1000	16.8	0.0918	91.0
„ No. 4	0.1000	16.77	0.0908	90.8
Coagula	0.1000	17.0	0.0920	92.0

From the data given in Table II it is clear that the diamagnetic susceptibilities of the powders tend to be constant when the particle size reaches 1μ . If this fall in diamagnetism is due to the impurity of the oxides in the powders, the antimony content of the samples should also tend to be constant at the particle size 1μ . This is exactly what is found to be, the antimony content of the powder No. 3 in the above table is very nearly the same as that of the powder No. 4.

3. *Removing the oxides from the powders and reinvestigating the samples so obtained magnetically.*—As given before, it is well known that whereas the metal itself does not dissolve in dilute hydrochloric acid, all its oxides are soluble therein. Hence in order to get rid of the oxides the powders were boiled with dilute hydrochloric acid and filtered and the process continued until the washings gave no test for antimony. The purified samples were then finally washed with extra pure acetone and left to dry in vacuum. When perfectly dry, they were reinvestigated magnetically and the results obtained are given in the Table IV. In order to facilitate comparison, the values of χ for these samples before freeing them from the oxides are also given in the last column.

TABLE IV.

Substance.	Wt.	Final reading.	Torsion given.	Magnetic susceptibility $\times 10^{-6}$.	Magnetic susceptibility before removing the oxide. $\times 10^{-6}$.
Antimony	0.1000 g.	242°.16'	114°.16'	-0.841	-0.812
Powder No. 1	0.1000	241°.57'	113°.57'	-0.834	-0.568
„ No. 2	0.1000	241°.54'	113°.54'	-0.823	-0.516
„ No. 3	0.1000	241°.0'	113°.0	-0.810	-0.499
„ No. 4	0.1000	240°.4'	112°.4	-0.805	-0.498
Coagula				-0.815	-0.529

It is clear from the above table that the powders practically regain the value for metal crystals after being boiled with hydrochloric acid, in which the oxides of antimony are soluble. This crucial test leaves no room for doubt that the observed fall in the diamagnetism of antimony is almost completely due to the oxide impurity. The fact that the powders do not exactly regain the value for metal crystals can easily be accounted, for on a visual observation it is seen that the surface of antimony crystals loses its metallic lustre even on almost an instantaneous exposure to the atmosphere. At small particle size, the surface increases very considerably and obviously surface oxidation shall affect the results appreciably.

4. *Powdering under inert liquids.*—If the oxide is formed by powdering in air, it is obvious that much less of it shall be obtained if the powdering is done under an inert liquid. The samples, therefore, should be much more diamagnetic than those obtained in air for the same particle size. So the powdering was done under liquid paraffin and the samples so obtained were washed free of paraffin by means of ether and dried in vacuum. They were later on magnetically investigated and the results are given in the following table.

TABLE V.

Initial reading = 123°·0′.		Current = 1 Amp.			
Substance.	Wt.	Final reading.	Torsion applied.	Magnetic susceptibility × 10 ⁻⁶ .	Particle size.
Water	0·1000 g.	254°·33′	131°33′	-072	...
Capsule	1·7480	219°·0′	96°6′
Antimony metal	0·1000	257°·18′	134°18′	-0808	...
Powder No. 5	0·1000	255°·8′	132°8′	-0758	...
„ No. 6	0·1000	253°·18′	130°18′	-0714	2μ

For the sake of comparison all the values of χ that have been obtained are plotted against the particle size in the accompanying graph. The curve for the samples powdered under liquid lies above that obtained for the samples powdered in air, and the one for the samples washed free of the oxide lies almost parallel to the χ axis, which

proves beyond doubt that the observed fall in the diamagnetism is due to the formation of oxide impurity.

I—Sb powders ; II—Sb powdered under water ; III—Sb (oxide removed).

SUMMARY AND DISCUSSION OF RESULTS.

The results arrived at in the course of this investigation lend further support to the view put forward by Bhatnagar and developed by us in our previous communication, that practically the whole of the observed fall in the diamagnetism in the case of these metals is due to the formation of oxide impurities formed during the process of powdering employed for colloidalisation. Bismuth metal, as shown in Table I acquires almost completely the regulus value of susceptibility after a complete removal of the oxide impurities. Antimony also shows the same value in the finely divided state as in the massive condition. We might, therefore, conclude that the magnetic susceptibility in the case of these metals is practically independent of the particle size. This view has recently been supported by the work of Lane (*Nature*, 1932, 130, 999) in the laboratory of Professor Gerlach, who has shown that the mass susceptibility of bismuth in the form of thin films ranging from 0.2μ to 15μ has almost the same value as the metal itself. It seems, therefore, that there are still some impurities

left behind in Rao's samples, (*loc. cit.*) which are responsible for a persistently low value obtained by him. Another possible explanation is suggested by the recent work of Seemann and Kussmann (*Naturwiss.*, 1931, 19, 309) to explain the effect of cold working on the susceptibility. The process of powdering may be regarded as akin to cold working and in this process probably some ferromagnetic impurities crystallise out resulting in a decrease in the magnetic susceptibility. Melting the coagula as Rao (*Nature*, 1932, 129, 545 ; *Indian J. Phys.*, 1932, 7, 35) has done, would render these impurities inactive resulting in an increase in diamagnetism. As suggested by Lane this point may be checked up by measuring the susceptibility of each powder under the influence of various field strengths which would be able to give us a valuable information with regard to the above point.

Absorption and adsorption of gases have recently been shown to affect profoundly the magnetic properties of α -manganese and it is just possible that this phenomenon plays a very important role at vanishingly small particle sizes in the case of these metals and it may be that the increase in susceptibility obtained by Rao on melting the coagula is due to the liberation of entrapped gases. Further work has therefore been undertaken in this laboratory in connection with the behaviour of metals at low particle sizes and the results arrived at shall be submitted for publication shortly.

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